

Improvising marketing strategies for movies based on digital feed: An Analytical Research Study

Abhijeet Mohanty
Bangalore, India
Mohanty.Abhijeet@tcs.com

Swaroop Krothapalli
Bangalore, India
Swaroop.k1@tcs.com

ABSTRACT

Digital feed from Social media and other web sources impart an in-depth insight into how audience interaction could help production companies assess the performance of their movie, and come up with pointers which may help them in enhanced targeting and improvising their marketing strategies to maximize returns.

Keywords: Box-Office, Twitter, Sentiment Analysis, Trends, web 2.0

INTRODUCTION

The multi-billion dollar Film Industry is an arena showcasing immense growth but, with extreme volatility. It surely is a place not for the faint hearted! And, anything associated even remotely to it, is subjected to a cut throat competition so fierce that, the margin for error is nil. Very few movies produced each year cross their break evens. And, only a handful of them strive to the status of 'Hits' or 'Blockbusters'. Overall, the returns altogether are discouraging.

In such a scenario, frugality and cost-effectiveness are of prime concern. Budgets are rigid and squeezing the maximum returns out of it, is the challenge which every production house faces. Lately, producers have made marketing their product as the number one priority so as to maximize viewership and ROI. PR agencies are working relentlessly on the movie decision timeline (Figure1) to meet the audience expectations and create that launch platform for a film with maximized viewership. Huge amount of efforts and money is now being diverted on formulating the perfect marketing and launch strategy. In the recent past we have seen production houses spend mammoth sums on this front. An effective strategy to market the movie to the right audience, at the right time with the right content in order to mobilize them to watch it, has become

absolutely necessary and imminent.

Figure 1: *Movie Decision Timeline*

The need of the hour is to analyse the audience preference and behaviour and turn it into actionable insights. The viable way to do so is to collect audience specific data pertaining to a bunch of movies and analyse them to identify pointers which could pave the path to understanding the positives and negatives, and identifying caveats which call out for action.

There is a wealth of untapped information about movies which is published over numerous web 2.0 websites. The only take is that the information is scattered. When looking patiently over the internet one could find information anywhere from the star cast, budget, launch date to the reviews, ratings and collections.

Pioneering internet technologies caused the advent of social media which has redefined human interaction beyond expectation. Now, one can interact with hundreds and thousands at the same point of time, share information in real-time, talk, discuss, debate as well as advertise. Homosapiens, the wise men indeed, are spending an increasing amount of time on these social media channels such as Facebook, Twitter, etc. to expand their human connect. Not only individuals, but business corporate of all sizes and nature are also on social media, showcasing their portfolio, advertising, collecting feedback and connecting with their customer. Because of this emerging trend, social media has now become the most preferred medium for brands to connect with their target audience. Apart from being a great engagement medium, social media can also provide rich insights on consumer behaviour, preferences and trends.

We have made an endeavour to analyse movie audience specific inputs from web 2.0 sources and social media, which could provide pointers pertaining to targeting, customer preference etc., which when fused with the right strategy could work wonders in terms of targeting, launch and elevating viewership.

In this paper, we use the chatter from Twitter.com and information from other web 2.0 sources, to identify caveats and generate insights which could foster better planning and data driven decision making. We envisage that a simple model built using inputs from Social Media can outperform market-based predictors. We further wish to demonstrate how sentiments extracted from Twitter can be utilized to improve the targeting, launch strategy thus mobilizing viewership and eventually, ROI.

DATA CAPTURE FOR THE ANALYSIS:

In general, the data capture includes chatter from Twitter.com; data from Google.com based on keywords engineered from movie summary, YouTube trailer views, Facebook likes, images posted across web, average user ratings, quantified music reviews, independent research data from web-sites like Boxofficemojo.com, Youtube.com,

Bigflix.com, imdb.com etc. Success parameters like week on week collection/revenue, number of launch theatre's etc. are also captured.

Data for select movies from above mentioned sources are collected, for a period of five to seven weeks. This time frame includes a pre-launch time frame of three weeks and a post-launch time frame of two weeks.

We have used API's to collect Social media feed logs from Twitter.com, facebook.com etc. Data captured from Twitter is extremely organized and hence forms the base of our analysis. Twitter.com captures data with respect to 3 major components of their Twitter.com user interface.

1. User Information: Twitter captures the basic user information of an account holder like their Names, Aliases, Location details, account creation date, source/medium used for making a particular tweet, number of peer followers of the particular user etc. Certain preference attributes like favourites, user description and other users which this particular user follows are also captured.
2. Tweet Message capture: The Twitter GUI limits each one of the tweet message of its users to a manageable 140 characters which enables it to capture the complete tweet as it is. It also captures the number of times this particular message was re-circulated or in Twitter lingo, Re-tweeted, prior to the current instance.
3. Hash tags: Any particular event or topic of discussion in a Twitter message is chain linked and referenced through a # (Hash) tag. Users can easily identify a topic of discussion by looking at the hash tag which has been tagged or referenced in a tweet. Engineering this novel concept of Hash Tags helps twitter gather structured chronicled data for different events, celebrities, sports, technology etc. and identify browsing traffic and trends which it could use for various initiatives, like advertisement, recommendations etc.

In our analysis, we have selected a total of fifteen Bollywood and regional movies released during recent times, belonging to varied genre, language and scale. For each one of these movies we have identified a list of forty keywords which viewers have used while talking about them. As an example; for the movie "Ramayya Vasthavayya", people have frequently used "#RV" while mentioning about the movie. In order to structure the inputs from chatter into comprehensible data points, we have modified the keywords in the data collection phase, with focus on viewer attributes such as opinion, preferences, demography etc.

These keywords were used for collecting data points from twitter on a daily basis for a period of 40 days from October 2, 2013 to November 10, 2013. We captured tweets at regular intervals for each keyword identified. The data provided by twitter database being in JSON format was converted to plain text using python scripting. At the end of 40 days, the entire data was aggregated to form the base of our analysis.

Overall, we captured close to 1,00,00+ tweets. The data was cleaned by removing tweets which were not in the context of movies. At the end of the data cleaning phase, we were left with 37,023 tweets, which were tweeted by 13,234 unique users.

Likewise, in Facebook we have collected the data from the Facebook movie page. When there were multiple pages for a movie, we considered the page which had the highest likes amongst all. The data points captured for each movie are: “Number of people talking about movie on a day” and “Number of likes the page has on each day”. Data for each movie is collected seven days before release of movie and seven days after release of the movie.

TWEET BASED OPINION/SENTIMENT ANALYSIS:

Sentiment or opinion analysis is a major tool which we use to understand the audience's perception and take on the movie. Social media with its inter connected users acts as a critique for a movie. Sentiment analysis helps in identifying caveats related to various aspects of a movie such as star cast, music, posters, trailers, story line etc. which could provide pointers for efficient marketing, targeting and sentiment driven corrective measures.

Sentiment based opinion of the tweets are evaluated using the ‘bag-of-words opinion Analysis' approach. The bag of words is an ensemble collection of words from two sources. One is from Professor Bing Liu who provided an English Lexicon of about 6800 positive and negative words. And the second sentiment lexicon is from the University of Pittsburgh having 8,000 words with positive/neutral/negative sentiment.

With a combination of unigram and bigram concepts used in standard sentiment analyses, we compiled 2 sets of words and phrases, one as 'Positive bag-of-words' and the second as 'Negative bag-of words'.

A python script crawled through each one of the tweet and provided with the frequency of positive words/phrases and negative words/phrases for a particular tweet. The sentiment score was estimated for each tweet using the formula:

$$Tweet\ Sentiment\ score = Number\ of\ Positive\ words/phrases - Number\ of\ Negative\ words/phrases$$

A tweet was then categorized into Positive, Negative or Neutral tweet based on its Tweet Sentiment Score (Table 1).

Tweet Sentiment score	Condition	Result	Tweet Sentiment Category
	Less than '0'	Negative	
equal to '0'	Neutral		
Greater than '0'	Positive		

Table 1: Tweet sentiment categorization based on Sentiment Score

Figure 2: Positive & Negative sentiment tweet distribution across movies(M1-M15)

TWEET PLATFORM ANALYSIS:

Social media accounts of Twitter, Facebook etc. may be accessed over a wide range of web and mobile platforms. The data we collected enlisted 317 such platforms. Overall 70% of the tweets were made using the website interface and official mobile application of Twitter.com. The major mobile devices using the official twitter.com app were Android, Apple and Blackberry.

With the advent of android revolution in India, there has been a drastic change in the way mobile based platforms were used for business and advertisement. At an individual level, Android has contributes to a significant 21% tweets.

Twitter.com website contributes to 18% traffic of the total chatter. Windows mobile has a negligible 1% tweets coming from its platform. We have classified all the third party applications like Hootsuite, Tweetdeck, Tweetcaster and 300 other platforms as “others”.

With the current trend observed we reckon, advertisers investing money on web and android mobile platform primarily would have a greater viewer reach.

Figure 3: Distribution of tweets based on different platforms

LOCATION ANALYSIS

Twitter allows each user to enter his location in a text field. A user has the freedom to write whatever he can in the location filed with no validation. We may also see many spelling mistakes entered in the location filed which may not be intentional. A location like Bangalore is entered in multiple ways like ‘Blore’, ‘Bangalore’, ‘Garden City Bangalore’, ‘Bengaluru’, ‘Banglore’ etc. There are many locations which only say country name, many are null, some say state name, and some values which doesn’t correspond to any location (Ex: “My dream land”) etc. Hence we don’t see structured data for location. We standardized all the locations by manually labelling it. This takes a considerable effort. But this labelled data can be used next time and we can build on

it. We then also arrived at two other data points which would say “State” and “Country” for each labelled data point. That way we are able to find the most famous cities, states and countries for Indian movies. It would help the revenue of the movie if we have a release in all the popular cities.

Figure 4: Top Indian cities with their % tweets

We also acknowledge the fact that twitter is popular with people living in cities, who prefer frequenting multiplexes for watching a movie. From the distribution of top cities we would like to convey that the movie release in multiplexes should be proportional to the distribution of users in top cities (Figure4).

Figure 5: Top countries with % distribution of tweets

Likewise we listed the countries where Bollywood movies are popular outside India. Hence, it would fetch production houses some money if the movie is released in these countries (Figure 5).

TWEETING BEHAVIOUR ANALYSIS:

We have categorized each tweet into multiple categories based on the keywords which portray the intent of the tweet. Most of the tweets fall under five major categories: Music, Trailer/Teaser, Movie Review, Promotion and Item Number.

Figure 6: *Tweet distribution based on movie attributes*

While analysing the trends for the movie songs we found that people mostly spoke about lyrics, their likes and dislikes for the song, sharing streaming links, download links, etc.

Item songs generate good buzz for the movie and foster interest and curiosity among the audience. The table shows the distribution of tweets among different categories based on: Movie without Item Songs vs. Movie with Item Songs. The table below shows a definitive indication that the buzz is significantly high when an item song video is launched as a teaser or for the promotion.

	Music	Trailer/Teaser	Movie review	Promotional	Item Number
Movie without Item Songs	34%	13%	24%	28%	1%
Movie with Item Songs	20%	24%	20%	6%	30%

Table 2: *Distribution of tweets among categories*

Before the movie release, songs and trailers created quite a good buzz in the social media space. Songs dominated the movie buzz pre-release in twitter almost by a factor of two.

Tweeters mainly shared the YouTube links of the trailer, while talking about the trailer. We found that movies which released more than one trailer prior to the release of the movie had better buzz and sentiment. During the launch weekend of the movie we saw tweets around movie reviews and their opinion about the movie. Movies which launched promotional activities in social media sites are also able to get good buzz about the movie.

The tweets which are about trailers, collections and sarcastic tweets got the maximum re-tweets. So when a production is trying to tweet about its movie, it should try to tweet more in above mentioned topics to maximize its reach.

Sentiment of each of the category for a movie is estimated based on the approach mentioned in the methodology. The sentiment could be: Positive, Negative or Neutral. We then estimate the metric, ‘Net Positive Score’ or NPS, for each movie in the above categories using the formula:

$$Net\ Positive\ Score\ (NPS) = Number\ of\ Positive\ Tweets - Number\ of\ Negative\ Tweets$$

Using NPS, we compute the “Promoters Score” for each category based on the formula:

$$\text{Promoters Score} = \frac{100 * \text{Number of Movies whose NPS} > 0 \text{ for that category}}{\text{Total Number of Movies in that category}}$$

Promoters score is an indicator of the importance of the Category in fostering a positive sentiment to the movie. This metric may be interpreted as the overall opinion of the category, which in our case, is the opinion about the music, the trailer, the promotional activities made etc. We may also infer from that, higher the Promoters score for a category, higher is the chance that this category was responsible for the buzz, the audience turn-up and eventually, revenue. The table below (Table 3) shows the Promoters score for all the categories.

	Music	Trailer/Teaser	Movie review	Promotional	Item Number
Promoters Score	100	40	88	71	60

Table 3: Promoters Score for each of the category

Music is one such thing which can connect with the audience at an instant. The buzz generated out of good music of a movie is tremendous. The same is evident from the data as well. With a Promoters Score of 100, Music seems to have created the right kind of buzz and anticipation for the movie. Production houses could take this as an insight and focus on releasing periodic updates of good songs and video songs to keep the buzz and anticipation for the movie, active and running.

Trailers have the lowest promoter score, which is an insight contrary to the general assumption that the success of a trailer is the benchmark for the success of the movie. Out of every three movie trailers, one trailer has a negative NPS indicating a negative outcome of the trailer campaign. Hence, a lot more effort and caution needs to be employed while designing and launching a trailer as it may accrue results which are counterproductive. This means that if a particular trailer is not well received by the audience, the overall image or sentiment of the movie could turn into negative. On the contrary, production houses could take corrective measures and alleviate the damage pre-launch. Trailers launched on weekdays have good response in terms of Youtube views, Facebook Movie page likes, Google results etc. as compared to weekend launches.

From the data we also found cases where the promotional activities are perceived as negative by the tweeters. Sarcastic negative tweets around the promotional activities have been significantly re-tweeted. So lot of caution and care should be exercised in doing promotional activities.

USER PROFILE ANALYSIS:

We have made an attempt to classify the users of twitter based on attributes relating to their user descriptions, likes, dislikes and other movie centric preference attributes. We have considered features like statuses (tweets made till date), account verified flag, number of followers an user has got, number of witter users he has been following, and user age in months (by calculating the difference between the date at which his/her

twitter account was created with respect to current date). We have also extracted certain attributes based on author description. We extracted keywords which indicated if he/she is a fan of a particular hero or heroine, Bollywood, his interests, profession etc.

We tested LDA on the author description data and we were able to classify users into 3 major buckets: hero/heroine fans, Bollywood followers and publishers. Though these three buckets were significant individually, collectively they only classified a meagre ~55% of the users.

In our second attempt to classify users, we employed K-Means clustering approach on the above mentioned attributes and were able to classify most of the users into four major buckets.

Cluster 1: Fan of a particular actress or actor

They are primarily fans of Khans of Bollywood and Hrithik Roshan in heroes. In heroines they are many fans of Deepika Padukone and Kareena Kapoor. They even mention about their favourite actor/actress in their profile description.

These people are active mainly during the launch or release of any of their favourite actor/actress movie or events. Of all the clusters users in this cluster are lowest by volumes. They are followed less number of people, they tweet less, and they also follow less number of people. They have the lowest user age. You find good number of spammers in this cluster. They appreciate fashion and trends followed by lead star cast in the movie and also love tweeting about it. They follow trends.

They usually like hero worship and love item songs in the movie. They do not mind typical concept movies. They encourage and participate in marketing campaigns launched by the movie. Irrespective of the verdict of the movie these users love watching the movie. They mainly watch the movie in non-multiplexes.

A good number of Indian actor/actress fans are also from Pakistan.

Cluster 2: Students

Most of the users who fall into this category are students in the age group of 16-25. They primarily like cricket and football as well. They play a major role in becoming a music album popular. They are active throughout the season. They tweet a lot about the songs they love listening to. They have the second lowest user age. Even though a few of them are fans of a particular hero, they are not hero worshippers.

Cluster 3: Working Professionals

They are engineers and working professionals in the age groups of 25-40. Here you mainly find fans of singers, director rather than star cast followers. They tweets relating to movies are less but their overall tweets are higher than the tweets of users in others clusters. They follow good number of people and are followed by descent number of people.

Reading books and photography are their hobbies. They are foodies. They do follow politics actively. They also tweet about movie songs as active as students.

The users here mostly catch the movie in multiplexes. They are movie buffs and love watching movies with novel story lines rather than commercial stories. They usually watch movie over the weekends. They are mainly located out of metros and major cities.

Cluster 4: Bollywood & Co-Brands

Here you find primarily the official handles of movies, publishers, reviewers, fan group handles etc. This cluster also consists of large brands who use movie promotions as an opportunity to create advertisements for themselves. They obviously have the highest followers. Hence, every tweet done by this cluster gets good number of re-tweets and favourites. For achieving maximum reach one should reach to the handlers/users here. If they reply to your tweet, or re-tweet it, it you would have maximum visibility and reach.

They frequently tweet about Bollywood news, spreading news and talk about the movie. These accounts are mostly verified and hence have a high degree of trust factor associated. They are the beginners of most of the viral marketing campaigns. This is the cluster that the production houses must target onto. A movie promo landing on the pages of such users is bound to have a greater reach. Tie ups with brands such as flipkart, myntra, cosmetic and jewellery brands could also help the movie reach a greater audience.

SUMMARY:

The Movie domain is still largely an unexplored territory in terms of data driven decision making. What we have shown in this paper is that, using the power of social media and web based information, we could help in segmenting the audience, identify his preferences and target him with the right content at the right time, so that the audience is continually connected to the developments of a movie right from its announcement date to the day it is finally launched. This not only increases the anticipation for the movie to be released, but also creates an atmosphere where it need not try hard to sell itself.

We have established that a continual focus needs to be put on each small aspect pre-launch, right from the launch of trailer, music, music video to the actual launch of the movie.

The work done in this paper is still premature and a lot of other ROI based analyses could be done to identify the right drivers of the buzz and popularity, so on and so forth.

Key references:

- [1] Sung Moon Bae, Kwan Hee Han, Ju Hyun Park, "Movie Recommendation based on User Profile and Reviews"
- [2] Sang-Hoon Kim , Youseok Lee [2013], Increasing Returns to Information and its Application to the Korean Movie Market
- [3] Sadi Evren Seker, "Sentimental versus Impact of Blogs", Istanbul Medeniyet University
- [4] Sihem Amer-Yahia, Ahlame Douzal, " Online Opinion Correlation for Large-scale Demographics"
- [5] Sitaram Asur, Bernardo A. Huberman [2010], "Predicting the Future with Social Media", HP labs.
- [6] Reggie Panaligan, Andrea Chen [2013], Quantifying Movie Magic with Social Search, Google Inc.
- [7] Mukherjee, Subhabrata and Bhattacharyya, Pushpak. "Sentiment Analysis in Twitter with Lightweight Discourse Analysis", IBM India Research Labs, IIT Bombay.
- [8] Andrew L. Maas, Raymond E. Daly, Peter T. Pham, Dan Huang, Andrew Y. Ng, and Christopher Potts." Learning Word Vectors for Sentiment Analysis", Stanford University.